

Some characteristics of Orissa fly ash with reference to mineral recovery

Niva Nayak and Chitta R. Panda*

Regional Research Laboratory (CSIR), Bhubaneswar-751 013, Orissa, India

E-mail : drpanda_cr@yahoo.com Fax : 91-0674-2581637

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Abstract : Three samples of Orissa fly ash without further grinding and size classification are characterized and compared for their potential use for mineral recovery. Compositions of major, minor and trace elements were determined by AAS, ICP and XRF analyses. As expected major mineral phases, like quartz, mullite, magnetite and hematite are identified by X-ray diffraction and IR spectroscopy. The particle size distribution study revealed a marked observation on the fineness of the particle which provides large active surface area for mineral leaching.

Keywords : Fly ash, metal extraction, minerals.

Fly ash is predominantly coal combustion residue containing inorganic matters and its characteristics may vary drastically because of the origin of the coal, the combustion method (boiler) and ash collection process. Fly ash residues generated in coal-fired power plants contain various constituents like silica, alumina, iron, titanium, calcium, magnesium, sodium, etc. of which alumina is the most valuable one. Hence, in addition to bauxite, extraction of aluminium from fly ash needs to be considered. Besides these major constituents it contains several trace elements, which are either present in organic or inorganic associations¹.

This paper deals with characterisation of fly ash with respect to major elements present with a view to develop suitable processes to extract valuable metal ions. It is realised that no single application is likely to consume all the fly ash generated in this country. Hence, metal extraction provides an additional option for increased utilisation of fly ash.

Results and discussion

The particle size and specific surface area of three fly ash samples have been undertaken by Malvern particle size analyser. Particle size distribution or fineness of fly ash is probably one of the most important factors, which plays a role in rate of chemical reactivity. Generally, fly ash particle ranges from 0.1μ to greater than 100μ in diameter and colour varies from grey to almost black. The cumulative particle size distribution pattern of three samples of fly ash is shown in Fig. 1 and the particle size distribution characteristics of these samples are presented

Fig. 1. Cumulative particle size distribution in Malvern particle size analyser.

in Table 1. The average particle size (D50) of TTPS, NALCO and RSP are found to be 19.84, 25.95 and

Table 1. Physical properties of fly ash samples

Properties	TTPS	NALCO	RSP
Particle size D50, μ	19.84	25.95	49.38
distribution by Malvern			
Particle size D90, μ	58.68	84.49	128.53
Particle size analyser D10, μ	5.89	6.77	11.03
Particle size analysis by SEM, μ	5	7	10
Specific surface area (m^2/cc)	0.5509	0.4664	0.3028
True density (g/cm^3)	2.09	1.58	2.13
Apparent density (g/cm^3)	0.941	0.975	1.0

49.38 μ , respectively. Ninety percent (90%) particles of these three different fly ash samples pass through 58.68, 84.49 and 128.53 μ and 10% particles pass through 5.59, 6.77 and 11.03 μ . Thus, TTPS sample comprises of very fine particles in comparison with NALCO and RSP fly ash samples.

Fig. 2. SEM Photomicrograph of fly ash samples : (a) TTPS, (b) NALCO, (c) RSP, (d) single particle of TTPS

The particle size of the three fly ash samples is also observed under SEM (Fig. 2) the result of which matches well with particle size analyser data. However, the grain sizes are measured and the average grain size determined for three fly ash samples are 5 μ , 7 μ and 10 μ for TTPS, NALCO and RSP, respectively. It is observed also by SEM the silicate particles are more in RSP than NALCO and TTPS.

The specific surface area obtained from the Malvern particle size analyser is essentially the external area of the material of different size range. The specific surface areas of these samples are 0.5509, 0.4464 and 0.3068 m²/cc for TTPS, NALCO and RSP, respectively. It is evident that TTPS samples having small particle size have larger surface area compared to the NALCO and RSP samples. Thus, particle size distribution and surface area data complement each other on the fineness of the sample.

Density measurement : It is observed that NALCO sample has lowest true density 1.58 g/cm³ compared to TTPS (2.09 g/cm³) and RSP (2.13 g/cm³) samples (Table 1). This may be attributed to the relative abundance of cenospheres in three ash samples. The result clearly indicates the presence of highest volume of cenosphere in NALCO fly ash compared to TTPS and RSP. The apparent/bulk density gradually decreases from RSP to NALCO to TTPS. Incidentally, the grain size also

decreases in same order. This may be indicative of the presence of heavy silicates in RSP having coarser size than that of other two samples

Microstructure by Scanning Electron Microscope : The electron micrograph of the TTPS, NALCO and RSP fly ash samples are shown in Fig. 2. All the figures exhibit glassy spheres (cenospheres) in different sizes with very small quantity of crystalline materials. The cenospheres show smooth globular surface with extremely small (submicron) dust like particles embedded on its surfaces. Fig. 2d shows electron micrograph of a typical spherical particle. Such spherical particles are formed due to surface tension and other hydrodynamic effect of environment². Fly ash constitutes several particles, which may vary in their morphology and chemical composition. This includes cenospheres (hollow spheres), plerospheres (solid spherical particles), needle and flaky shaped particles. The needle and flaky shaped particles are most likely represent sillimanite/mullite and kaolinite, respectively. Warren and Dudas² have identified three parts of the cenosphere, which are of chemical importance. The uppermost part contains an exterior glass hull over which some salt grains are deposited. The middle part is a layer consists of crystalline phases i.e. mullite and the interior part is the glass matrix. These cenospheres are probably formed by melting, fusing and sintering of clay minerals³. The kaolinite flakes are present in minor amounts and further supported by XRD pattern.

Mineral phases by XRD : Inorganic constituents present in coal directly control the mineralogy of fly ash. During the combustion of coal, its mineral matters undergo considerable changes. Though XRD is the most common method to determine the mineralogical characteristics of fly ash, some reflections are difficult to assign unambiguously to any distinct mineral phase, some do not appear or some gives a broad peak. This is because during the ash fusion a variety of aluminosilicate compounds are formed which occur in amorphous state.

Fly ash contains both the amorphous and crystalline phases. The major minerals present in the three fly ash samples observed in XRD are quartz, mullite, hematite, magnetite, sillimanite and spinel ferrite (?) and are given in Fig. 3. These mineral phases are identified at their corresponding 'd' values as per JCPDS data file. Large humps and irregular background in diffractograms indicate the predominance of glassy or amorphous constituents in ash, which is confirmed from the diffused diffraction pattern observed at the 2 θ regions of 25–40° of the diffractogram^{4,5}. Relative abundance of mineral phases in the three fly ash samples as observed from their XRD patterns are :

Quartz > Mullite > Sillimanite ≥ Magnetite > Hematite

XRD pattern of RSP fly ash shows the absence of sillimanite phase. Besides, some other expected minerals which may be present in <5 wt% are difficult to be identified by XRD. The presence of phases like quartz, mullite and hematites are also confirmed by the IR observations.

degree region, except RSP sample.

IR observation : Identification of mineral phases is further supported through infrared spectra analysis of fly ash sample. Strong absorption bands are seen at 3470–3438 cm^{-1} for stretching vibrations and at 1631–1610 cm^{-1} for bending vibrations for adsorbed water molecule for all the samples (Fig. 4). Minor variations in absorption peak values in different ash samples are shown in Table

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffractogram of fly ash samples.

In all the three samples 100% peaks for hematite and magnetite are seen at 2θ values of 33.1 ($d = 2.61$) and 35.1 ($d = 2.53$), respectively. These minerals are expected to be derived from the pyrite oxidation in parent coal combustion⁶. Similarly, the quartz peaks (100%) are identified at 2θ values 26.4 ($d = 3.343$), which is considered as the major phase. All the identified quartz is high temperature quartz and is expected to be from the parent coal or by disintegration of hydrous aluminosilicates (clay minerals) at high temperatures.

The mullite phases which are observed at 2θ values 26.2 ($d = 3.39$) are suggested to be formed through solid-state reactions primarily from kaolinite, and to a lesser extent from high-Al illite and illite/smectite. Thermodynamic modeling by Evgueni *et al.*⁷ suggests that mullite and its molten phase co-existed between 1100 °C and ~1500 °C with the mullite/melt ratio decreasing with increasing temperature. As the particles cooled, mullite recrystallised from its molten phase except in the fluxed outermost layers. Thus, mullite phase is observed for all the three fly ashes at 2θ 26.2-degree region. In addition to, sillimanite phases are also seen at 2θ 40.5-

Fig. 4. IR spectra of fly ash samples.

2. The peaks at 1094, 913, 792, 459 cm^{-1} obtained for TTPS samples are in agreement with the absorption peaks for quartz as reported by Gadsden⁸. Weak bands are seen

Table 2. Prominent IR absorption bands of different mineral phases

TTPS	Observed		Reported	Identified minerals
	NALCO	RSP		
	vibrational frequency (cm ⁻¹)		vibrational frequency (cm ⁻¹)	
3449	3470	3438	3430s	Adsorbed water
1631	1610	1630	1640be	Adsorbed water
1170	1180	1165	1170sh	Quartz/Haematite
1094	1088	1089	1090vs,b	Quartz
913	913	910	915vw	Quartz
835	835	845	825-20d	γ Alumina
792	796	784	796 m	Quartz
750	750	760	752-45d	γ Alumina
-	700	700	700	Mullite
620	620	600	580p	γ Alumina
560	557	560	560-570	Haematite
459	459	456	462-50	Quartz

at 835, 750 and 620 cm⁻¹, which show the presence of γ Al₂O₃. Similarly, presence of mullite phase is seen at 700 cm⁻¹ in NALCO and RSP sample, whereas this is not observed in TTPS sample. Although the IR spectra show a weak band at 700 cm⁻¹, the mullite phase is not identified clearly. This may be due to the presence of appreciable amount of silica present in fly ash. Presence of a sharp peak at 560 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of hematite in fly ash. However, a shoulder at 1170 cm⁻¹ attributes to both i.e. quartz and hematite. Similar absorption peaks are seen for the other two samples of NALCO and RSP. Thus, the IR spectra for all the three fly ashes show the presence of absorption band for quartz, hematite and mullite at the respective positions.

Chemical characteristics : The chemical composition of Indian fly ash consisted largely of silica, alumina, iron and carbon along with significant percentage of calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium, titanium and variable amounts of trace elements. Intensive studies have been undertaken on the chemistry of fly ash throughout the world. Chemically, all naturally existing elements are found to be present in fly ash and the major matrix elements like Si, Al and Fe along with significant percentage of Ca, K, Na and Ti are present⁹⁻¹¹.

The major and minor element distribution of the three different fly ash samples have been presented in Table 3. The result indicates that silica (SiO₂) is the primary constituent and other matrix elements are aluminium and iron in the form of oxides. The minor elements include calcium oxide (CaO), magnesium oxide (MgO), potassium

Table 3. Major (%) and trace (ppm) elements in fly ash

Oxide element	TTPS	NALCO	RSP
SiO ₂	59.490	61.426	63.610
Al ₂ O ₃	29.091	27.334	25.048
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.901	4.587	6.759
TiO ₂	1.902	1.785	1.651
K ₂ O	0.722	0.722	0.795
CaO	0.993	1.203	0.602
MgO	0.332	0.332	0.415
Na ₂ O	0.129	0.143	0.143
P ₂ O ₅	0.619	0.619	0.321
LOI	2.580	1.690	0.51
V	252.02	183.43	197.47
Cr	168.90	138.03	133.90
Mn	197.79	392.21	451.96
Co	35.03	22.72	18.30
Ni	90.49	60.33	48.62
Cu	112.43	63.53	49.58
Zn	118.02	62.49	54.79
Sr	209.36	135.46	146.07
Ba	356.87	381.50	597.74
Pb	135.05	90.01	41.64

oxide (K₂O) and sodium oxide (Na₂O). From the table it is observed that the silica (SiO₂), aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) and iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) are closely within the specified range as described in Indian Specification (IS-3812) and by other workers^{12,13}. This is because almost all the thermal power plants use high ash (35–40%) coals in their boiler. However, there is distinct difference in the composition of fly ashes of TTPS, NALCO and RSP. The aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) content is higher in TTPS (29.091%) than NALCO (27.334%) and RSP (25.048%). The iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) content varies in the reverse manner i.e. RSP > NALCO > TTPS. The silica (SiO₂) content of three fly ashes varies from 61.426 to 63.61%.

The loss on ignitions (LOI) which accounts for the unburnt carbon, sulphur, moisture and other volatile matters is generally considered as an indicator of carbon content in fly ash. The LOI are found to be 2.78, 1.69 and 0.413% for TTPS, NALCO and RSP, respectively. The particle size distribution and low value of LOI clearly depict the absence of much higher carbon content. The thermogravimetric measurement provides additional support for the presence of water molecule and volatile matter. A broad exothermic peak at 130 °C shows the initial loss of H₂O and further a broad exo peak at 315

°C attributes to the loss of CO₂, SO₂, and a suite of organic compounds.

The trace elements in fly ash generally originate from their parent coal and may have inorganic or organic association. Over 90% of the trace elements derived from the inorganic constituent of coal are some of the toxic metals, like zinc, mercury, cadmium, arsenic and lead. Some trace elements like germanium, beryllium, titanium, and boron come from the organic constituent of coal. Some other trace elements like As, Co, Cu, Ni, Zn, Hg and Tl may be associated with pyrite (FeS₂)³. Presence of some important elements like vanadium, chromium, manganese, copper, zinc, lead, cobalt, nickel, strontium and barium are detected by X-ray fluorescence measurements and are given in Table 3 along with standard sample SRM 2691. From Table 3 it is observed that the elements like Cr, Co, Ni and Cu show a decreasing trend from TTPS to NALCO to RSP. Since the concentration of Fe₂O₃ is more in RSP and NALCO than TTPS it is expected a reverse trend for these pyrite associated elements. The finding is attributable to particle size which determines the elemental concentration of the respective samples. Similarly, Mn and Ba concentration show an increasing trend from RSP to TTPS. The elements like Sr and V also show a decreasing trend but the concentration is found to be more in TTPS and less in NALCO ash samples. Although the concentration of Pb shows a decreasing trend the Pb concentration in TTPS is much higher (135.05 ppm) than RSP (41.64 ppm). The result is obvious since the association of trace elements is related to fineness of the particle.

The leachability of trace elements is more complicated and varies with the distribution of different phases. A number of investigators^{11,14-16} have identified the presence of trace elements in fly ash and observed that the concentration of As, Cd, Cu, Ga, Mo, Pb, S, Sb, Se, Tl and Zn increase with fineness of fly ash particle while V, Mn and Be exhibit non-uniform dependence on particle size. According to Adriano *et al.*¹⁷ the mechanism of such dependence is not known with certainty. It has been hypothesized that the metal concentration dependency with respect to particle size is the result of volatilization of elements upon combustion followed by surface condensation and deposition as the ambient temperature drops. The less volatile element like Al, Ba, Ca, Ce, Co, Eu, Fe, Hf, La, Mg, Mn, Rb, Sc, Si, Sm, Sr, Ta, Th and Ti show little tendency towards partition according to particle size. There are also elements like Be, Cr, K, Na, Ni, Sc, U and V that would exhibit intermediate behaviour.

Similar observations on elemental concentrations were also reported¹⁸⁻²⁰.

pH and electrical conductivity : The acidic and alkaline nature of fly ash depends upon the specific chemical constituents present in it. All the three fly ashes are acidic in nature and the pH of the three fly ash samples are 5.1, 6.2 and 6.7 for TTPS, NALCO and RSP, respectively. The acidic pH may be due to the release of oxides of sulphur (SO₂ or SO₃) adsorbed on highly reactive and extremely fine fly ash particles, producing H₂SO₃ or H₂SO₄ in solution²¹. The exo peak at 315 °C of TG/DTA also supports the presence of SO₂ and CO₂ which are responsible for acidic nature. The acidic nature of fly ash is also due to the presence of little Ca and considerable amount of Fe. All the three fly ashes show low alkali and alkaline metal content, which provide adequate evidence for the acidic character of the sample. The released H⁺ ion interaction with Fe₂O₃, aluminosilicate minerals and MnO are also found to be responsible for the acidic character of fly ash²².

The electrical conductivities (EC) of these fly ash samples are 0.813, 0.151, 0.088 ds/m for TTPS, NALCO and RSP, respectively. The low conductivity can be explained on the basis of dissolution of fewer amounts of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions (surface salts like Na₂O, K₂O, CaO and MgO) in aqueous medium. The low pH is also an indicative of non-existence of free CaO (lime) in the samples, which has potential surface leaching properties causing land and water pollution. Since the present study concerns with ashes of Indian sub-bituminous coal with high silica content the presence of low CaO, MgO and SO₃ are expected^{23,24}.

Conclusion :

Fly ashes from three different power plants of Orissa, viz. TTPS, NALCO and RSP, have been characterized chemically and mineralogically in order to understand the association of inorganic mineral matters, with a purpose to find out the suitability of aluminium extraction and other strategic metals from fly ash. The mineral matter in all the fly ash samples is dominated by quartz, mullite, hematite and magnetite. The investigated fly ashes also contain several trace elements along with major and minor elements like Si, Al, Fe, Ca, Mg, Na and Ti. Fineness of the fly ash particle is also advantageous for extraction of metal ions by leaching methods. Moreover, the low calcium content of ashes makes it highly suitable for the mineral recovery in an acid leached process. Attempts have already been taken in this laboratory to extract high pure aluminium²⁵ and other possible metals from TTPS

fly ash. The systematic chemical and mineralogical study gives further insight to the possible utilisation of valuable metals available in fly ash.

Experimental

The samples studied are three high ash sub-bituminous coal and collected from the electrostatic precipitator of three different coal fired thermal power stations of Orissa, viz. Talcher Thermal Power Station (TTPS), National Aluminium Company (NALCO) and Rourkela Steel Plant (RSP). The as received samples, without any further grinding and size classification are subjected to various studies like mineralogy, morphology, particle size and chemistry. The chemical characterisations were determined by wet chemical methods and by using various instruments, viz. Flame Photometer (Elico, Model CL-22D), Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Varian Spectra AA-20), Inductive Coupled Plasma Spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Plasma-400). The trace metals were analysed by WDXRF (Philips PW 2404) Spectrometer. The pH and EC were also determined by Orion Model-1260 instruments. The density measurement was also done by the displacement of toluene using pycnometer.

The particle size analysis was carried out by Malvern particle size analyser (UK, Model-3600). Scanning Electron Microscope (Jeol JSM 840) attached with an Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analyser (EDS) has been used for morphology and crystal structure of fly ash. The X-ray diffractogram for fly ash samples was carried out on Philips PW 1400 using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. IR spectra of the samples were taken with Perkin-Elmer 823 spectrometer in the range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The TG/DTA analysis was also carried out using Shimadzu DT 40 thermal analyser.

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